

SHORT NOTES

Confirmation of the Structure of Vanadyl Salicylate

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The tetravalent vanadium is known to form complexes with a number of ligands¹⁻⁴. The study of the reaction between vanadyl sulphate and potassium salicylate shows the formation of 1:2 complex and a structure has been suggested for the compound⁵. The present work has been undertaken to confirm the suggested structure by means of potentiometric and analytical studies.

An ethanolic solution of vanadyl sulphate (B.D.H. analysed sample), and AnalaR salicylic acid were used. A Pye pH meter was used for potentiometric studies.

Moles of salicylic acid added.

FIG. 1.

Potentiometric titration of 10 ml of 0.1N-VOSO₄ with salicylic acid.

NaOH added (ml).

FIG. 2

Curves 1 and 2 represent titration of 20 ml of 0.5M salicylic acid with molar NaOH in presence of 5 ml of ethanol and 5 ml of vanadyl sulphate (0.05M) respectively.

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Potentiometric titration (Fig. 1) of vanadyl sulphate with salicylic acid shows a break at 1:2 ratio, indicating formation of a disalicylate. The chelation reaction can be represented as:

Addition of alkali to the reaction mixture neutralised the hydrogen ions produced by chelation. the number of equivalents of alkali required being equal to the number of H^+ ions liberated. The potentiometric titrations of vanadyl sulphate with NaOH in presence of 2 and 3 moles of salicylic acid (curves 1 & 2, Fig. 3) show a sharp inflection at $m=4$ (m =equiv. alkali per mole of the metal ion). indicating liberation of 4H^+ ions, i.e., the H atoms from the $-\text{OH}$ groups also.

In order to confirm further, potentiometric titration of salicylic acid alone and in presence of a small amount of vanadyl ions (curves 1 & 2, Fig. 2) was carried out with

Moles of NaOH added.
FIG. 3

Curves 1 and 2 represent titration of 10 ml of 0.05 M-VOSO_4 with 0.5 M-NaOH in presence of 2 and 3 moles respectively of salicylic acid per mole of vanadyl ion.

NaOH . At particular pH values, the differences in the values of m on curves 1 and 2 indicate that 4H^+ ions per molecule of the disalicylate chelate are liberated during its formation, i.e., 2H^+ ions per salicylic acid molecule.

Isolation of the Solid Compound.—The solid compound was isolated by neutralising the mixture of ethanolic solutions of vanadyl sulphate and salicylic acid in 1:2 ratio with ethanolic NaOH solution and refluxing the whole. On analysis, the solid compound was found to have 14% V (IV) and 12.5% Na, in agreement with the formula suggested for the chelate.

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